

Recruitment Ratio, Facilities Provided and Problem Faced by the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes Female Teachers in Higher Education

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Abstract- India in its Seventy-six years of independence, the government has taken various programme and schemes for the development of the poor and the disadvantaged peoples. The National Education Policy-2020, has stressed on implementing inclusive and equitable quality education at all level starting from School education, Higher education, Professional education, to adult education and life-long learning to support the SDG agenda. Without education no plan can be successful and to make successful education teachers at all level must be prepared for quality education for all.

Keywords: Female teacher, scheduled castes, scheduled tribes, higher education.

1.0 INTRODUCTION:

Education is a powerful means of passing experiences for the growth of physical, mental, moral and spiritual qualities that helps in the development of an individual in a society. It exposes people to new thoughts and ideas and provides necessary skills and capacities to make a person competent enough to control over the environment for fulfilling the possibilities in life.

In search of new ways for overall well-being of all people, all lives in the land and water in our planet earth, the sustainable development summit-2015, held in New York adopted the agenda-2030 containing seventeen sustainable development goals (SDG) aiming to promote prosperity by removing the poverty and protecting environment. In India, the government has taken various programme and schemes for the development of the poor and the disadvantaged peoples since independence and it has crossed Seventy-six years of independence, the literacy rate was 74.04 percent as of 2011 census reports.

India has been taking good efforts to reach the SDG target by 2030 and the National Education Policy-2020, has stressed on implementing inclusive and equitable quality education at all level starting from school education, higher education, professional education, to adult education and life-long learning to support the SDG agenda. Without education no plan can be successful and to make successful education teachers at all level must be prepared for quality education for all. A study was conducted to find out whether all categories of people, irrespective of sex could represent equally at the higher education level, and the study was designed to find out whether female teachers of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes were recruited proportionately in the colleges and whether they could avail the facilities as recommended by the University Grants Commission or they faced problem in discharging their duties.

2.0 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The study will have immense significance in highlighting the recruitment strategies in the colleges, problems encountered by the SC and ST female teachers in the institutions and in the processes of their personal career advancement schemes. The outcomes will support in the formulation and implementation of policies for women wellbeing as well as their involvement in policy making processes

3.0 LITERATURE REVIEW:

The education system has been changing from time to time, the previous education of national context has been changed to global education and the one-time education has been modified to life-long education. In the present time the learner-centric education has been implemented from the original teacher-centric education. Such a modification creates new challenges to the education system and its practice as mentioned in Higher Education in India: Issues, Concerns and New Directions, UGC (2003).

R. Naru & R. P. Choudhary (2022) reported that there was no good relationship in between the academic head and the college teachers. Teachers faced problem about their job confirmation, that creates pressure on the mind of young teachers. The academic head makes delay in career advancement of the young teachers.

UNESCO and ILO (2008) recommended a wide range of issues for improving teacher status that include continuing training, recruitment, advancement and promotion, security of tenure in service, part-time service, professional freedom, supervision and assessment, responsibilities and rights, disciplinary procedures, participation in educational decision-making, negotiation, conditions for effective teaching and learning and social security.

UNESCO (2012) introduced a set of operational priorities for teachers supporting quality learning and of teacher status in terms of raising the quality standards of the teaching profession worldwide and their social recognition by reinforcing the mechanism.

Symeonidis (2015) argued that National education system faced various challenges some of which had threatened to teacher status e.g. global economic crisis, privatization, shortage or oversupplies, under-financing and governmental attitude. The study also reported salaries and working condition were two of the most crucial factors related to teachers' occupational status and personal self-esteem.

4.0 OBJECTIVES

4.1. To study ratio of SC and ST women teachers in the affiliated colleges of Dibrugarh University of Assam

4.2. To study the facilities provided and problems faced by the SC and ST women teachers in the affiliated colleges of Dibrugarh University of Assam

5.0 RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

5.1. What is the ratio of SC and ST women as teachers in affiliated colleges of Dibrugarh University of Assam?

5.2. What are the facilities provided and problems faced by the SC and ST women teachers in the affiliated colleges of Dibrugarh University of Assam?

6.0 METHODOLOGY:

In the present study, both primary and secondary data were collected to fulfill the specific research objectives. Data regarding the teachers' profile, recruitment procedure, physical and academic facilities were obtained from the head of the institutions by using an Information Schedule. Data from the SC and ST female teachers were collected through Questionnaires. Apart from the collecting data through sample survey, secondary data also collected as required for the study.

6.1 Population:

The study comprised of all the affiliated Colleges (excluding professional and women colleges) of Dibrugarh University of Assam. All total 127(one hundred and twenty-seven) affiliated Colleges in seven districts of Upper Assam and all SC and ST female teachers were included in the population. Seven districts were namely Tinsukia, Dibrugarh, Sivasagar, Jorhat (undivided), Golaghat, Lakhimpur and Dhemaji⁸.

6.2 Sample:

The sample of the present study was chosen in general and co-educational degree Colleges, and for this study 20% of the colleges of Dibrugarh University from each of the 7 districts of Upper Assam were selected by employing lottery method, which was found to be 25 numbers of colleges. There were 27 female teachers of which 5 SC and 22 ST communities were selected out of total 54 SC and ST females were selected by incidental sampling method and data were collected for the study.

7.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION:

7.1 Findings and discussion on objective-1: Ratio of SC and ST women teachers in the affiliated Colleges.

Table-1: Percentages and ratio of SC and ST women teachers in the affiliated Colleges of Dibrugarh University

Social groups	SC		ST		Others		Total		
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M+F
Nos. of Teacher	21	14	72	40	332	298	425	352	777
% of Teachers	2.70	1.80	9.27	5.15	42.73	38.35	54.70	45.30	100
Ratio of SC/ST women teachers to Total teachers (rounded)	1:20	1:25	1:6	1:9	1:1	1:1	-	-	-

Figure-1: Percentages recruitment of SC and ST women teachers in the affiliated Colleges of Dibrugarh University

There was a total of 777 teachers, who have been working in sampled affiliated Colleges of Dibrugarh University, during this study period. The Table-1 illustrates clearly the percentages of teachers in the affiliated Colleges of Dibrugarh University. There were 54.70% male and 45.30% female teachers, of which 2.70% was SC male and 1.80% SC females. Whereas the percentage of other category teachers was 42.73% male and 38.35% females. Ratio-wise there was only 1.00 SC female out of 25 total female teachers, which is very low in comparison to the women teacher of others category, where the ratio was 1 out of 1 of total female teachers.

The ST teachers comprised of 9.27% male and 5.15% females; whereas the others category represented with 42.73% male and 38.35 % female teachers. Ratio-wise there was 1 ST female teacher out of 9 total female teachers, whereas the ratio of women teachers of others category was 1 out of 1 of total female teachers. It can be concluded that the representation of women of SC and ST were very low in teaching profession in comparison to women of others categories in these affiliated colleges under Dibrugarh University.

It can be concluded that there was a gender inequality among the teachers in the sampled affiliated colleges of Dibrugarh University in 2018-19, which was also reported by Arulasamy in 2011 and the recruitment as a whole was not proportionate for representing all categories of people, especially the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes communities. Becker M. (1999) made a comment regarding gender inequality that society cannot flourish if inequality of gender prevails in a society.

Regarding the facilities provided it was found that only a low percent of teachers was availing the research facilities including of both in PhD and M Phil degree programme and in a personal level minor research programme. Some of these teachers were benefitted by career advancement schemes and had completed teachers' Orientation programme and Refresher courses. But some of the teachers reported that they had been over loaded by the class hours in the colleges. The overall environment in the college campus was reported to be good.

8.0 CONCLUSION:

There was a low recruitment of Scheduled Cases and Scheduled Tribes females as a teacher in the affiliated colleges, of course the recruitment was not a same day event, but as a whole the percentage of female teachers, and especially of Scheduled Cases and Scheduled Tribes categories were remained very low. All teachers were not benefitted by the career advancement schemes of UGC.

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